

Toxicological Studies of Thallium Dicarboxylates

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The toxic effects of thallium are well documented¹. The well known circumstances of thallium poisoning² are suicide, homicide and accidental poisoning. Further, thallium is an important element with a wide variety of applications³ including the uses as a rodenticide and pesticide. Toxicities of thallium(I) and thallium(III) compounds have also been reported by various workers⁴.

The present study reports the toxicities of various thallium dicarboxylates synthesised⁵⁻¹⁵ in our laboratory and compares with the toxic effects of various dicarboxylates of univalent and trivalent thallium.

Results and Discussion

The results (Tables 1 and 2) show that among the compounds tested, pyridinium trisoxalatothallate(III) and thallium(I) oxalate are relatively effective and quick-acting poisons. Caesium, barium and strontium compounds are more poisonous compared to ammonium and potassium salts of thallium(III) oxalates (Table 2, 1-7). The toxicity of the other dicarboxylatothallate(III) compounds (Table 2, 8-15) are similar, thallium(III) malonate being the most toxic among them.

The high toxicity of the pyridinium trisoxalatothallate(III) is probably due to the presence of pyridinium ion in the compound which forms very toxic pyridinium chloride¹⁶ in the body of the animal. Another highly toxic compound is thallium(I) oxalate. From a comparison of the similar compounds (Tables 1 and 2), it is clear that thallium(I) compounds are more poisonous than thallium(III) compounds.

Thallium(I) oxalates are found to be more toxic among the thallium compounds tested and it has LD₅₀ values of 3-10 mg/kg when compared with the other compounds with LD₅₀ values in the range 20-30 mg/kg. However, different monovalent thallium compounds really become converted into thallium(I) chloride immediately after having been introduced into the organism, their biological action and toxic

effect should be identical when these compounds are administered in doses which contain equal quantities of thallium. This increased activity of thallium(I) oxalate may not be attributed to the release of oxalate ion during the reaction with the body fluids, as the oxalate released or thallium(I) present is too low to be lethal. Hence, this increased activity appears to be due to

Fig. 1. Toxicity of thallium(I) oxalate : (x) 1, (O) 24, (●) 48 and (Δ) 72 h. some synergistic effect due to the simultaneous presence of thallium(I) and oxalate.

When these compounds were administered to the animals, onset of death in the animals was found to be quicker with lower or intermediate doses, but delayed with the higher doses. But the survival percentage was found much lower with the higher doses than with

TABLE 1—TOXICITY OF THALLIUM(I) COMPOUNDS*

Sl. no.	Compd.	Animal	Death occurred in h with dose (mg / kg)			
			3	10	30	100
1.	Thallium(I) oxalate ^a	A	0.5	0.5	1	0.5
		B	Safe	1	1	30-44
2.	Thallium(I) monohydrooxalate ^b	A	Safe	1	0.25	1
		B	Safe	Safe	Safe	5-21
3.	Thallium(I) trihydrodioxalatodihydrate ^c	A	Safe	1	6-23	24-30
		B	Safe	3	0.5	24-30
4.	Thallium(I) bis(oxalato) diaquothallate(III) trihydrate ^d	A	Safe	Safe	Safe	30-45
		B	Safe	Safe	Safe	30-45
5.	Thallium(I) chloride	A	Safe	Safe	Safe	2
		B	Safe	Safe	54	22
6.	Oxalate (as sodium salt)	A	—	Safe	24-36	24-36
		B	—	16-24	24-36	24-36

*The dose is expressed in terms of the amount of thallium per kg body weight of the animal for all the thallium compounds; A and B are mouse one and mouse two to which the compound is administered. ^a Ref. 5. ^b Ref. 6. ^c Ref. 7. ^d Ref. 8.

TABLE 2—TOXICITY OF THALLIUM(III) COMPOUNDS

Sl. no.	Compd.	Animal	Death occurred in h with dose (mg / kg)			
			3	10	30	100
1.	Ammonium bis(oxalato) diaquothallate(III) monohydrate ^a	A	Safe	Safe	78-86	36-45
		B	Safe	72-82	72-82	36-45
2.	Potassium bis(oxalato) diaquothallate(III) dihydrate ^b	A	Safe	Safe	Safe	24-32
		B	Safe	72-82	72-82	36-45
3.	Caesium bis(oxalato) diaquothallate(III) dihydrate ^c	A	Safe	Safe	2	2
		B	Safe	72-82	2	6-12
4.	Barium bis(oxalato) diaquothallate(III) monohydrate ^d	A	—	6-12	6-12	6-12
		B	—	6-12	6-12	6-12
5.	Strontium bis(oxalato) diaquothallate(III) monohydrate ^e	A	—	3	3	2
		B	—	3	3	24-36
6.	Thallium(III) bis(oxalato) diaquothallate(III) ^f	A	Safe	Safe	Safe	30-45
		B	Safe	Safe	Safe	30-45
7.	Pyridinium trisoxalatothallate(III) ^g	A	1	15 min	30 min	1
		B	Safe	15 min	30 min	24-32
8.	Thallium(III) hydroxymalonate ^h	A	—	2	18-24	2
		B	—	30-24	30-24	6-18
9.	Ammonium succinatothallate(III) ^h	A	Safe	Safe	6-12	6-12
		B	Safe	Safe	30-48	6-12
10.	Ammonium glutaratothallate(III) ^h	A	Safe	Safe	4	30-42
		B	Safe	Safe	50-62	30-42
11.	Ammonium adipatothallate(III) ^h	A	Safe	Safe	6-12	30-42
		B	Safe	Safe	6-12	30-42
12.	Ammonium pimelatothallate(III) ^h	A	Safe	Safe	2	30-42
		B	Safe	Safe	30-42	30-42
13.	Ammonium suberatothallate(III) ^h	A	Safe	Safe	2	30-42
		B	Safe	Safe	6-12	30-42
14.	Ammonium azelenatothallate(III) ^h	A	Safe	Safe	2	6-12
		B	Safe	Safe	120-132	30-42
15.	Ammonium sebacatothallate(III) ^h	A	Safe	Safe	1	2
		B	Safe	Safe	2	8-16
16.	Thallium(III) oxide	A	Safe	Safe	96	24
		B	Safe	Safe	Safe	36-48
17.	Thallium(III) chloride	A	Safe	Safe	3	47
		B	Safe	Safe	Safe	60

^a Ref. 5. ^b Ref. 9. ^c Ref. 10. ^d Ref. 11. ^e Ref. 12. ^f Ref. 13. ^g Ref. 14. ^h Ref. 15.

lower doses. To verify this observation, studies are carried out on thallium(I) oxalate (the most poisonous among the Tl compounds studied) taking larger batches of 10 animals for each dose instead of 2. The results of such study are shown in Fig. 1. From the curves it is clear that the number of animals died in 1 h is maximum in 30 mg/kg dose. The curve representing the number of animals died in 24 h shows that the 300 mg/kg dose is very effective whereas the 10 and 30 mg/kg doses are more effective than the 100 mg/kg dose. The curve representing the death in 72 h shows a regular trend according to the increasing dosage. From these observations it appeared that thal- lous oxalate is possibly acting in two ways – the one route being quick but less effective while the other slow but more effective in causing death of the animal.

Experimental

Sodium oxalate (A.R., B.D.H.) and chemically pure glycerol were used. A known volume of stand- ardised thallium(III) chloride solution was evaporated to dryness and mixed with glycerol and used for the study. All other compounds were prepared as per the reported procedures⁵⁻¹⁵.

Determination of toxicity and LD₅₀ values :

The glycerol suspension of the compounds was used for the toxicity study. Each compound was ad- ministered in four different logarithmic doses based on the thallium content (3, 10, 30 and 100 mg/kg). In the primary screening a pair of mice were administered with each dose orally by means of syringe and oral feeding needle. The animals were then observed for 4 h for their behavioural and autonomic signs and later kept in cages for 4 days and observed for the mortality. The LD₅₀ value of the compound was taken as the corresponding dose which could bring out death in 50% of the animals to which the dose was ad- ministered.

References

1. D. OLMER and A. TAN, *Compt. Rend Soc. Biol.*, 1909, **65**, 742; A. G. LEE, "Chemistry of Thallium", Elsevier, New York, 1971; P.A. SHAW, *J. Pharmacol.*, 1933, **48**, 478; W. L. DOWNS, J. K. SCOTT, L. T. STEADMAN and E. A. MAYNARD, *Am. Ind. Hyg. Assoc. J.*, 1960, **21**, 399; P. FLAMM, *Biol. Chim. Kerap. Sper.*, 1926, **13**, 27; C. O. V. MARITUS, *Dent. Arch. Klin. Med.*, 1953, **200**, 596; M. LAVY, *Neder- land Tijdschr. Geneeskunds*, 1927, **71**, 2611; G. V. BEDFORD, *Can. Med. Assoc. J.*, 1928, **19**, 660; M. GIARBASI and I. TRAINA, *Pediatrica Rev.*, 1937, **45**, 385.
2. J. J. G. PRICK, W. G. S. SMITH and L. MULIER, "Thallium Poisoning", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1955; C. J. POLSON and R. N. TAFTERSALL, "Clinical Toxicology", Pitman Medical Publishing Company, Lon- don, 1969.
3. ETHEL BROWING, "Toxicity of Industrial Metals", 2nd. ed., Butter- worths, London, 1969.
4. A. BUSCHKE and B. PEISER, *Klin. Wochschr.*, 1922, **1**, 2182; N. A. IRIN, P. HOFMAN, N. N. MELNIKOV and A. M. AVFESIAN, *Arch. Intern. Pharmacodyn.*, 1938, **58**, 371; N. A. IRIN, *Arch. Intern. Pharmacodyn.*, 1938, **60**, 377.
5. S. R. SAGI, K. V. RAMANA and M. S. P. RAO, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1979, **31**, 285.
6. S. R. SAGI, M. S. P. RAO and K. V. RAMANA, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1980, **40**, 311.
7. S. R. SAGI, M. S. P. RAO and K. V. RAMANA, *Miller Thermal Analysis*, 1982, **2**, 499.
8. S. R. SAGI, M. S. P. RAO and K. V. RAMANA, *J. Thermal. Anal.*, 1981, **20**, 93.
9. S. R. SAGI, K. V. RAMANA and M. S. P. RAO, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1979, **33**, 187.
10. S. R. SAGI, K. V. RAMANA and M. S. P. RAO, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1980, **19**, 575.
11. S. R. SAGI, K. V. RAMANA and M. S. P. RAO, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, **59**, 336.
12. S. R. SAGI, K. V. RAMANA and M. S. P. RAO, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1981, **20**, 1214.
13. S. R. SAGI, K. V. RAMANA and M. S. P. RAO, *Miller Thermal Analysis*, 1982, **2**, 506.
14. M. S. P. RAO, Ph.D. Thesis, Andhra University, 1978.
15. G. S. P. RAJU, Ph.D. Thesis, Andhra University, 1978.
16. "Registry of Toxic Effects of Chemical Substances", U.S. Depart- ment of Health Education and Welfare, Rockville, Maryland, 1975.

